

ELECTORAL REFORMS AND CONSOLIDATION OF DEMOCRACY IN NIGERIA: PROSPECTS AND CHALLENGES IN THE 21ST CENTURY

By

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Abstract

This study is concerned with the various electoral reforms embarked upon by Nigeria's Electoral Management Body in the build-up to 2015 general elections. The paper adopts institutional approach and applies a qualitative method in drawing its conclusions. It also argues that the successes recorded are largely informed by the institutional reforms geared towards conducting acceptable, free, fair and credible election in Nigeria. The paper finds out that efforts at consolidating democracy in Nigeria can be fast-tracked, close up electoral reforms are sustained and positive attitudinal change are imbibed by all stakeholders to abide by the rules and regulations guiding democratic project. It also suggests sustenance of the reforms so the country can meet electoral standards obtainable in advanced democracies.

Keywords: Election, Electoral Reforms, Democracy, Democratic Consolidation.

Introduction

Democracy evaluations have been a side of interest to many researchers in social science. Years of research, teaching, and consulting in political science left a conviction that research on democratic consolidation is increasingly brushing up against the limitations of existing democracy measures. Coppedge and Reinicke (1990) opine that "It is difficult to conduct democratic studies without considering immense contributions of

concept of election". In other words, election is critical in the successful study of democracy. It is arguable that election in developing democracies, like Nigeria do not signal the completion of the transition to democracy, but rather foster a long process of liberalization and boost a self-reinforcing power to promote increased access to decision-making by the large spectrum of the citizenry through their representatives. Election also facilitates institutionalization of genuine political participation and

confers legitimacy to the government, thereby hastens the pace for democratization. Every modern definition of democracy must include participatory and contested election as the legitimate procedure for the translation of rule by the people through workable executive, legislative and judicial powers. Albeit, election alone does not sufficiently, make a democracy work, yet no other institutional practice precedes participatory, competitive and credible election in engendering self-government. One of the overall thrust of this paper is to examine various reforms embarked upon by INEC that largely informed successful execution of 2015 General Elections and how it adds value to internalization of democratic values by the stakeholders and strengthens institutionalization of democratic practice in Nigeria. The paper adopts qualitative method which involves collections, analysis and interpretation of data by observation of people's action and utterances. It refers to the meaning, definition, attributes, symbols, metaphor and description of the objects. It is imbued with subjectivity and applies unique method of collection of information usually individual, in-depth interview, questionnaire and focused group discussion. The paper interviewed officials and ad hoc staff of INEC, leaderships of the two dominant Political Parties –APC and PDP–and focal persons of Civil Society Organizations, a sizeable number of electorates and some personnel of selected Security Agencies, who partook in 2015 General Elections.

In achieving this, purposive sampling method- which entails considerations of respondents based on needed qualities- age, gender, occupation, experience and interest- is adopted. This paper applies qualitative approach in interpreting data collated.

The Concept of Election

Election is an integral part of a democratization which enables the citizenry determine fairly and freely who should lead them at every level of government periodically and take decisions that shape their socio-economic and political destiny; and in case they- leaders- falter, still electorates possess the power to recall them or vote them out in subsequent elections. Obakhedo (2011) aptly defines election “as a major instrument for the recruitment of political leadership in democratic societies; the key to participation in a democracy; and the way of giving consent to government and allowing the governed to choose and pass judgment on office holders who represent the citizens”. In its strictest sense, there can never be a democracy without election. Huntington (1991), pointed out that, a political system is democratic ‘to the extent that its most powerful collective decision-makers are selected through fair, honest and periodic elections in which candidates freely compete for votes, and in which virtually all the adult population is eligible to vote’. In its proper sense, election is a process of selecting the officers or representatives of an organization or

group by the vote of its qualified members (Nwolise, 2007). Anifowose (cited in Bamgbose, 2012) defined election as the process of elite selection by the mass of the population in any given political system. Iyayi (2005) submits that “election provides the medium by which the different interest groups within the bourgeois nation state can stake and resolve their claims to power through peaceful and legal means”.

Electoral Reforms

Electoral reforms are changes of some element of an electoral system, including suffrage rights, the size or number of seats in the assembly, the magnitude or number of seats in the districts, the formula to allocate seats or make a winner, and the ballot form permitting or restricting the voters’ choice of parties and candidates. In the long term, major electoral reforms have expanded suffrage rights, replaced indirect elections with direct elections by majority rule, and done the latter with mixed systems and proportional representation rules. Traditional electoral systems based on plurality or relative majority rule in multi-seat districts were used in traditional compact communities in late medieval and early modern times (Benoit, 1995). They are still used in a significant number of local government elections in which it can be presumed that citizens share some clearly identified, broad common interest.

The Concept of Democracy

The word democracy is of Greek origin and consists of the words demos (often translated as “full citizens”) and kratos (“to rule”). Despite their common terminological base, the two schools are very different with regard to how and by whom popular rule should be exercised. Democracy is a political system established on the basis of rule of the many, in contrast to the rule of the few (e.g., oligarchy or aristocracy). The multitude of forms of democracy is mirrored by an abundance of theoretical concepts and models of democracy in the social sciences that this makes it a contested concept. Baradat (1988) simply defined democracy as a system that creates opportunity for a popular decision making. They believed that democracy is nothing more than an agreement among citizens that the majority vote will carry the issue or that one branch of government will not reach too far into the functions of another branch, and also a system that every individual is basically equal to all other individual, and that each has certain inalienable fundamental rights.

The Concept of Democratic Consolidation

Originally, the term “Democratic Consolidation” was meant to describe the challenge of making new democracies secure, of extending their life expectancy beyond the short term, making them immune against the threat of authoritarian regression. This

normalization requires the expansion of citizen access, development of democratic citizenship and culture, broadening of leadership recruitment and training, the functioning of a mature civil society and political institutionalization (Dode, 2010). By the term democratic consolidation, it means the deliberate political process in a polity by which democracy is “so broadly and profoundly legitimized among its citizens that it is very unlikely to break down”. This consolidation of democracy involves behavioral and institutional changes that normalize democratic politics and narrow its uncertainty. Consolidation requires that habituation to the norms and procedures of democratic conflicts regulation will be former Labor Party, the Liberal Party, the Progressive Party, etc who occasionally participate in electoral competition (Ouyang cited in Dode, 2010). For such countries, two parties are important in influencing the alternation of political power.

Institution

Institutions are important because as entities they form such a large part of the political landscape, and because modern governance largely occurs in and through institutions. Institutions also matter because they (or at least actors within them) typically wield power and mobilize institutional resources in political struggles and governance relationships. Institutions are also said to matter because they are seen as shaping and constraining political behaviour and decision making and even the

perceptions and powers of political actors in a wide range of ways (Bell and Head 1984). Hence, in institutional terms, students of politics have analysed party systems, the rules of electoral contests, government bureaucracies, legislatures, constitutions, the judicial system, as well as large institutional complexes made up of the government and the gamut of public institutions we call the ‘state’ (Fenna, 1998). There have also been extensive studies of supra-national institutional complexes such as the United Nations, the European Union and other international institutional regimes that help regulate economic relations, the environment or international trade (e.g. the World Trade Organisation). There have also been studies of ‘non-state’ institutions such as business corporations and trade unions.

Theoretical Framework

Institutional approach is that part of the social sciences which studies how institutions- i.e, structures and mechanisms of social order and cooperation governing the behavior of two or more individuals- behave and function according to both empirical rules (informal rules-in-use and norms) and also theoretical rules (formal rules and law) (Abbot, 1998). This field deals with how individuals and groups construct institutions, how institutions function in practice and the effects of institutions on each other, on individuals, societies and the community at large (Adams, Elisabeth, and Ann, 2005). Since institutional approach is focused

on the systematic study of people's collective behavior, its ability to explain major political, social, or historical events by the systematic, regular, publicly documented behavior of groups of individuals (Almeida, and Linda, 1998) is always emphasized.

Institutionalism as an approach is divided into sociological, historical and political institutionalisms. The three institutionalisms have different origins and emphases in their strategies of research, as well as different advantages and disadvantages. Sociological institutionalism is a response in part to views of organizations, such as the resource dependence model, and interactions among states, such as world systems theory, that neglect cultural structures and processes in explanations. Notwithstanding their similarities and differences, theoretical and methodological insights, research gains, analytical problems, and prospects for the study of politics, institutionalism focus study of the development of public policy, the terrain on which many advances in political sociology and political science have taken place (Amenta, 1998).

In the study of policy, sociological institutionalism focuses on quests for legitimation in political organizations and tends to focus on processes of policy imitation and diffusion and especially on surprising convergences in forms of institutions and policies. Some scholars think that the process by which a democracy becomes consolidated

involves the creation and improvement of secondary institutions of the democracy. Linz and Stephan's thesis (cited in Abbott, 1992), for example, is that democracy is consolidated by the presence of the institutions supporting and surrounding elections. O'Donnell (1988) believes that the institutionalization of electoral rules is not the most interesting feature of democratic consolidation. His approach is to compare the formal institutional rules (for example the constitution) with the informal practices of actors. Consolidation of democracy on this view is when the actors in a system follow (have informally institutionalized) the formal rules of the democratic governance.

The Justice Uwais' Electoral Reform

Against the backdrop of widespread disenchantment by Nigerians and international community, and late president Umar Yar'Adua's open admission during his inaugural speech that the general elections of the 2011 general polls that brought him to power was seriously flawed and promised to correct the weakness in the electoral system, Electoral Reform Committee (ERC) under Justice Muhammad Lawal Uwais - Ex-Chief Justice of the Federation - was mandated to fashion out how to improve the quality of future elections. The Committee after a thorough job, submitted its findings in December 2008. Among the most momentous reforms were those to increase INEC independence and fiscal

autonomy. Some of the recommendations of the ERC were implemented and became handy in the 2011 elections under the watch of Professor Attahiru Jega the INEC Chairman. The 2011 election was applauded by both local and international observers of being credible and transparent. But the conduct of the 2011 elections was not without some challenges before, during and after the election (Abdullahi, 2013).

The Uwais' Electoral Reforms Committee set to effect major reforms to address the following issues among others: Political opportunism, Political patronage and god-fatherism, lack of choice for electorate through illiteracy, money politics, zoning in politics, conduct of elections as warfare (rigging, etc), absence of penalties for political crimes and ideology in politics and political parties, geo-political endorsements, lack of internal democracy in political parties, lack of independence for and interference in INEC by the executive, delayed announcement of results, deliberate delay in resolving election petitions and citizenship and residency debacles (Iyayi, 2010). Specifically Obianyo and Emesibe (2015) submit that the Uwais' Electoral Reforms Committee proposes the following recommendations:

Justice Uwais' Committee recommendations on Electoral Reforms attempted to deal with some of these issues but it is understood that, both the Executive and the Legislature have

virtually passed a death sentence on the recommendations of the Committee (Aderemi, 2005). Against this background, it is clear that the Campaign for 'One Man, One Vote; One Woman, One Vote' could not be realized without addressing the above problems. It is also believe that many members of the political class who claim to support the campaign of 'One Man, One Vote; One Woman, One Vote' were doing so because they not only understood this connection; but they fully recognized that the problems could not be resolved within the framework of the current structure of society.

Independent National Electoral Commission, Electoral Reforms and the 2015 Elections

INEC under the leadership of Prof. Attahiru Jega came up with a comprehensive blueprint providing detailed electoral process guiding the conduct of 2015 general elections in Nigeria. It is a complete departure from the past as the robust leadership painstakingly offered a radical procedure to ensure credible, free, fair, and transparent and elections that goes a long way in deepening democracy and improving the legitimacy of governance.

Challenges

One crucial challenge encountered by INEC is the centralization of recruitment system. A sizeable number of on-line prospective ad hoc staff has been identified to have falsified their data.

Many ad hoc staff and NYSC members were reported to have abandoned their duty posts, especially in remote areas of the state. Another hiccup was the inability of INEC to re-issue PVCs to voters whose cards were stolen, damaged or lost. INEC therefore, faced the task of dealing with cases of missing cards and transfer of residents. Political parties' rallies were marred by isolated cases of violence and intimidations by rival armed militias. The violence was largely between supporters of the two dominant political parties in Nigeria- APC and PDP. Although, security agents were promptly deployed to restore order and normalcy, their efforts were largely affected by logistics and numerical limitations.

Research Findings and Discussions

Below is the thematic discussion of data collated through interview, which explains the relevance of electoral reforms to the overall effort at consolidating democracy in Nigeria.

1. Effectiveness of Election Management Body in Ensuring Credible Elections

“The 2015 General Elections was an improvement of previous episodes. The success recorded was largely informed by a number of reforms and innovations introduced by INEC to ensure better service delivery and restore local and international confidence in Nigeria’s electoral process”(Interview, 2017).

This clearly show that electoral reforms and innovations implemented by INEC, positively improved its service delivery, couple with sufficient funding and assistance from donor agencies.

2. Extent to which Election Enhances Legitimacy of Government

“The 2015 election legitimizes the entire political system in Nigeria. It is a known fact that before the elections citizens were expressing their angst not only to the government of the day but to the entire polity. Now there is renewed hope and citizens are also ready to cooperate with leaders to fast-track developmental efforts” (Interview, 2017).

The general commendation greeting the outcome of the election signifies its general acceptance and enhancement of the government legitimacy. As one of the key functions of election, improved legitimacy also signifies democratic consolidation, as it guards against democracy reversal.

3. Challenges of Conducting Free and Fair Election in Nigeria

“Political parties are independent entities guided by relevant electoral acts that fields and promotes candidate for electoral contests. However, in Nigeria these entities pose serious challenges to the conduct of credible, fair and free elections in that they inherently lack internal democracy, cohesion, organization, vision, mission and ideology. As a result of these, electoral

contests become a matter of life and death” (Interview, 2017).

The ability of INEC and other election stakeholders to confront challenges faced before, during and after the general elections is a major pointer to an improved capability and internalization of rigorous task of electioneering in Nigeria.

4. The 2015 Elections and Consolidation of Democracy in Nigeria

“Consolidation of democracy is achievable through concerted efforts and willingness of the people to demand for better deal which is embedded in the ability of government to reinvigorate agencies to attain certain measures of improvement that will restore public confidence in the electoral process” (Interview, 2017).

“Future of democracy in Nigeria rests squarely in the overall readiness of the stakeholders to abide by the rule of the game and accept election outcomes in good faith. It also rests in improved institutional delivery, healthy contests and limited money in politics (Interview, 2017).”

“The 2015 election could be said to be fair in that it leaves the defeated political parties with no option to seeking redress in the court of law. This is achieved through the concerted efforts of INEC, security agencies, political parties CSOs etc” (Interview, 2017).

“The 2015 election made possible for Professor Attahiru Jega-led INEC to raise the bar high and restore integrity of the electoral process (Field Interview, 2017).”

“The 2015 election is free, fair but not credible. At least, the electorates got what they voted for at the centre but not in states and constituencies” (Interview, 2017).”

“There are a lot of instances where security compromise was recorded in many Polling Units. INEC harbors many staff with criminal tendencies as evident in many cases being adjudicated in various parts of the country involving both regular and ad hoc staff”(Interview, 2017).”

5. Mobilization and Participation

“CSOs and NGOs are key partners in any democratic project. They provide ample opportunities for mobilization, sensitization and observation of electoral process. Over 20 COS were registered in Sokoto state during the 2015 elections. They were involved in campaigns, rallies, election monitoring, vote’s collation and announcements of the results (Interview, 2017).”

“High participation recorded during the 2015 election underscore improved voters’ education and awareness, emotional attachments, people willingness to demand for better

treatment as in making sure that their votes really counted.” (Interview, 2017).

6. Election Observation/Monitoring

“The 2015 election created space for election observation and monitoring by a number of CSOs and Interest groups both from within and outside the country. It is recorded that more than 80% of Polling Units were manned which goes a long way in checking criminal and political predatory proclivities to rig elections in favor of their preferred candidates or parties” (Interview, 2017).

7. Electoral Violence

Electoral violence is often the result of monumental disagreements and disapprovals registered by concerned individuals and groups due lack of confidence in the outcomes of an election. Reasons for eruptions of violence could be socio-economic policies of the sitting government, poor role of candidates and political parties who at times cash in inflamed on narrow sentiments to drive home points or engender supports, youth restiveness, poor civic education and compromised electoral management body (Interview, 2017).

The 2015 General Elections attracted much interest from the media- print, electronic, social and traditional. Most of the media houses were involved in transmission of jingles, adverts, documentaries and promos for candidates and political parties. However, many of them were involved

in unprofessionalism in their bid to outwit one another through sponsored campaign of calumny and character damages. Civil societies who were majorly visible in urban centers played key role in information dissemination, especially on the need for peaceful electioneering processes. In similar vein, a number of foreign bodies such as NDI, IRI, EU and Commonwealth observer groups also acknowledged the elections a step forward in the annals of elections in Nigeria. Ms Robin Carnahan of NDI says “...election was the second best in series that appears to mark a turning point for Africa’s most populace country” (Alfa, Alhassan and Adah, 2015). Ms. Constance Newman of IRI submits that “the overall conclusion is that INECs professionalism, the role of security agencies and reduction of cases of election-related violence” informed the success of 2015 election (Alfa, Alhassan and Adah, 2015). Mr. Alojz Peterce, the chief observer of 141- member EU-EOM stated the “.....election means an important step in strengthening democracy in Nigeria”. Mr. Festus Mogae, leader of Commonwealth Observer Group says “Nigeria shakes off the stigma of flawed elections in that in reflected the will of Nigerian people” (Alfa, Alhassan and Adah, 2015)

Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

The research topic is Electoral Reforms and Democratic Consolidation in Nigeria. The following objectives are set to be achieved: to study how Reforms by

INEC is geared to ensuring credible elections in 2015; to identify challenges in conducting free, fair and credible elections in Nigeria; to ascertain the extent to which election enhances legitimacy of government; and to assess impacts of election in ensuring democratic consolidation. The research was carried out on the basis of the following assumptions: That Implementation of effective reforms by INEC is key to improving election outcomes and heightening the chance of consolidation of democracy. Broadly the research found out that reforms and innovations improve the capacity of the INEC in effectively conducting free, fair and credible elections. It also found out that though conducting election entails confronting a number of challenges institutional, attitudinal and environmental, right attitudes on the part of stakeholders and adherence to laid down rules and regulations go a long way in executing acceptable elections thereby enhancing democratic consolidation. That elections conducted under free, fair and credible atmosphere boost legitimacy of the government and assuage emotional and political feelings of aggrieved people. The research also discovered that for democracy to become deepened, rooted and embedded in the society, the elite and masses alike must conform to procedures, practices, rules and regulations guiding political contests and mediation of conflicts through institutionalized setting, and avoid resort to undemocratic measures. Specifically, this research finds out that:

1. The 2015 elections to a large extent were free and fair due to reforms, innovations and improvements of electoral process by the INEC.
2. Electoral violence, though experienced in some polling units, was largely localized and therefore could not invalidate the outcome of the elections.
3. To a large extent 2015 general elections' outcome reflects the true choices of the electorate. This is due to fact that defeated candidates and parties were reluctant to challenge victory of their opponents at election petition tribunals.
4. Law enforcement agencies and judiciary lacked technical and physical capacity to prosecute electoral fraudsters in many occasion.
5. Civil Society Organizations mainly concentrated their activities in urban centers and few areas adjacent to state capitals, thereby neglecting remote and rural areas where a larger chunk of voters reside.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Comprehensive institutional reforms including INEC, Security Agencies and Judiciary for efficient service delivery.
2. Political parties should be reconstructed afresh or rebuilt on new principles that truly allow for members to participate at all levels.

- Officers elected must also not be subservient to some Godfathers, incumbent Executive whether at the Federal, State or Local Government level.
3. Political actors should imbibe politics of ideology, mission and vision tailored in comprehensive and workable socio-economic blueprint for the overall progress and development of Nigeria.
 4. Far reaching decentralisation (political and administrative) schemes of entire government structures in Nigeria for engendering of local autonomy, local initiatives and sanitising political contests should be given utmost attention. Nigeria's governmental structure is cumbersome, obsolete and dormant. This is evident in the outward and pronounced incapacity of various federating units to provide basic social amenities to citizenry.
 5. Introduction of E-Voting system, i.e. Electronic Voting System (EVS) is one of several forms of automated voting methods which employs computer technology devices to improve several aspects of the electoral process. This goes a long way in improving the quality of elections, minimizing waste, curbing expenses and logistics and restoring public confidence on the electoral process.

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